

EVALUATION OF LIGHTNING DAMAGE RESISTANCE OF PANI-BASED CONDUCTIVE THERMOSETTING COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, newly developed PANI-based conductive thermosetting composite is proposed to improve a lightning damage resistance of composite materials. The authors have been developed conductive thermosetting resin using Dodecylbenzenesulphonic acid (DBSA) as a dopant and Divinylbenzene (DVB) as crosslinking polymer to enhance the rigidity. In this paper, modified one-step process to prepare the prepreg sheet comprises of carbon fibre fabric and PANI-based resin enables which improves the electrical conductivity, homogeneously, and storage stability. The resultant conductivity of PANI-based composite was 148 [S/cm] in in-plane and 0.73 [S/cm] in out-of-plane which is 5 times in and $3.5 - 7.0 \times 10^2$ times greater than that of conventional CF-epoxy composite, respectively. In order to confirm the improved lightning resistance property, the PANI-based thermosetting composite is subjected to the simulated lightning current with 100kA peak current generated with an impulse current generator. As a result of a simulated lightning current test, whereas the conventional CF-epoxy composite shows large defect in outside and inside, the newly developed PANI-based thermoset composite was hardly damaged by the simulated lightning current. It was confirmed that the superior electrical conductivity of CF-PANI composite quite effectively suppresses the internal damage due to lightning strike.

1 INTRODUCTION

Applying carbon fibre - epoxy resin composite to the large size structure such as an airframe, wind turbine blade, and automobile is enables us to reduce their weight and maintenance cost because of the

superior mechanical and fatigue/corrosion resistance of the composite to conventional metal materials [1], [2]. On the other, because of inferior electrical and thermal conductivity of CFRP to conventional metal materials, lower lightning damage resistance becomes major issues. Lightning current attachment causes serious damage due to Joule heating effect, matrix resin decomposition, acoustic shock, electro magnetic force, and so on [2-6]. Especially in composite airframe design, a special attention should be taken into account against a lightning strike event. In general, LPS (Lightning Protection System) comprise of metallic mesh or metallic foil is applied on the surface of composite structure to prevent lightning damage. However, applying LPS increase a total structural weight, manufacturing cost. Furthermore, even if LPS is applied to composite structure, it is difficult to completely protect from lightning damage. Complicated repair process is usually required after lightning strike event; it increases maintenance time and downtime of commercial aircraft. Therefore, it is highly required a new solution which can improve a lightning damage resistance of composite material itself.

In the past studies, several approach have been attempted to improve an electrical conductivity of insulating matrix resins. One of the possible approaches to improve the electrical conductivity of composite is to mix the conductive nanomaterial (ie. carbon nanotube, carbon nanofiber, metal nanoparticle, and graphene) with matrix resin as filler [7-11]. Our previous research shows the effectiveness and potential to improve the lightning damage resistance of CFRP with cup stacked CNF fiber as conductive fillers [12]. Nano composites with conductive fillers and polymer, however, generally have a drawback with respect to manufacturing process. Furthermore, to applying the nano materials, environmental risk cannot be neglected; sometimes, a volume of nano particles spread into atmosphere with an explosive evaporation and decomposition of matrix resin because of lightning current attachment.

One of the promising approaches to solve this problem is to use conductive polymer instead of applying conductive nano fillers. PANI (polyaniline) and its derivatives are on of the most studied intrinsic electrically conductive polymer in recent years [13-21] because of their high conductivity, good environmental stability, and low cost manufacturing process. The authors recently developed a highly conductive thermosetting polymer system that comprise of PANI, DBSA as a dopant and DVB as a crosslinking polymer [22, 23]. This polymer system shows ideal properties for a matrix of CFRP to enhance electrical properties and lightning damage resistance.

In this present study, newly developed PANI-based conductive thermosetting composite is proposed to improve a lightning damage resistance. Lightning damage resistance was examined by performing a simulated lightning current test by using an impulse current generator. Damage behaviour during discharge was observed with high-speed imaging technique, and resulting lightning damage was examined with visual inspection and ultra-sonic inspections. The efficiency of enhanced electrical property of PANI-based conductive thermosetting composite was evaluated by comparing with a result of conventional CF-Epoxy composite laminate.

2 MATERIAL AND SPECIMENS

3.1 Conductive polymer system

The authors have been developed conductive thermosetting polymer system with PANI, Dodecylbenzenesulphonic acid (DBSA) as a dopant and Divinylbenzene (DVB) as crosslinking polymer to enhance the rigidity [22, 23]. In general, preparing PANI based conductive thermoset resin require complex process; mixing of PANI and dopant, doping, mixing of PANI/dopant/polymer/curing agent, and subsequent curing by adding heat [13, 14]. Then our previous study [23] proposed one-step process for preparation of PANI based composite. The newly proposed process uses DVB as a polymer matrix and blends of PANI/DBSA/DVB are prepared by centrifugal mixing. Where DBSA act both as a dopant and a curing agent, the reaction of doping of PANI/DBSA and curing of composite undergo simultaneously with a single heating process.

In this present study, the modified mixing process by using three-roll milling machine instead of previously applied centrifugal mixer is newly proposed to achieve more homogeneous and high quality blends of PANI/DBSA/DVB. In addition to DBSA, PTSA was also used as a dopant to increase the electrical conductivity of cured resin. A binary dopant system (DBSA and PTSA) was

chosen to satisfy the stability of polymer blends, manufacturability of CFRP, and high conductivity. DBSA mainly acts as a dopant for PANI and a curing agent for DVB, whereas PTSA contributes to increased electrical conductivity. The blending weight ration of PANI/DBSA/PTSA/DVB was fixed to 15/31/4/50 wt% in this study. The detailed description of chemical reaction, conductivity mechanisms, and development process of PANI-based composite is described in [24].

3.2 Specimen preparation

Laminated composites were cured by conventional prepreg-based process with the prepreg sheets comprised of PANI-based conductive resin and plane-woven carbon fiber sheet of TR3110M (Mitsubishi Rayon Co., Ltd, TR30-3K fibers, 200g/m²). The prepreg sheet was prepared with newly developed process that previously described. PANI (Regulus Co. ltd.), DBSA (Kanto Chemical Co. Inc.), and TPSA (Tokyo Chemical Industry Co. Ltd.) are mixed to form a PANI/DBSA/PTSA blend by the three-roll milling process in the ratio of 30/62/8 in percentage by weight, subsequently mixed with DVB (Sigma-Aldrich Co.) at room temperature with the ratio of 50:50wt% with the blends. A single layer of the plane-woven carbon fabric is impregnated with the resin to make CF/PANI prepreg.

Eight plies of the prepreg sheets were stacked and cured at 110°C for two hours with the hot press. The stacking sequence was: $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_8$, and thickness of resultant laminate was 1.6mm. For the comparison, conventional CF/Epoxy laminate was also fabricated using identical carbon fibers fabric and XNR/H6815 epoxy resin (Nagase Chemtex Co. Ltd.) with a VaRTM (Vacuum-assisted Resin Transfer Molding) [25] process. The specimens were cut out in size of 150×150mm from both the parent laminate of PANI-based laminate and CF-Epoxy laminate.

3 EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Experimental setup

Simulated lightning current was applied to the specimens using an impulse current generator (Otowa Electric Co. Ltd.,) (Fig. 1). The impulse current generator having capability of applying the standard combination wave form of component A, B, and C, which defined in SAE ARP-5412 [26]. Figure 2 represent a testing setup of a support jig and a discharge electrode. Specimens were fixed with a picture frame type copper jig, which were connected with the ground of the impulse current generator. In this setup, only the edge of specimen was retained by base plate and cover flame that were screw clamped each other. An applied impulse current was measured by using a current transducer (Model 1423 produced by Pearson Electronics) connected with the ground line and a digital oscilloscope (DPO 3034 produced by Tektronix, Inc).

Generally, lightning damage phenomenon is concluded for a quite short time with emission of highly intense flash. In order to observe damage process of composite struck by simulated lightning current, an ultra-high-speed video camera (HPV-1 produced by Shimadzu Co. Ltd.) was applied. A triggering signal for the high-speed camera was transmitted from the oscilloscope connected with the current monitor measuring return current.

Fig. 1: Impulse current generator (Comp. A)

Fig. 2: Schematic of support jig and discharge electrode

3.2 Testing conditions

In this study, modified simulated current of Component A defined in SAE ARP-5412 [25] was applied. Whereas the original Component A wave form has -200kA peak current, in this study, peak current of -40kA (A/5) was applied. The applied simulated lightning current waveform was exponential, which can be characterized by the time to peak current (t_1) and the time to decay to fifty percent of its maximum amplitude (t_2). Figure 3 represents a typical result of simulated lightning current measured by the oscilloscope connected with the current monitor. Table 1 represents the simulated lightning current condition tested in this study; where action integral shows the applied electrical specific energy.

The simulated current was applied in the center of specimen surface as arc entry; the gap between the tip of discharge probe and specimen surface was set to be 2mm.

Fig. 3: typical result of measured applied simulated lightning energy

S/N	Material	Peak current [kA]	Wave form	Action integral [A ² s]
E-1	CF/Epoxy	40.0	29.6/78.6	76,103
E-2	CF/Epoxy	38.8	34.1/79.5	72,991
P-1	CF/PANI	41.2	30.9/77.8	82,141
P-2	CF/PANI	41.2	26.7/76.2	82,410

Table 1: Testing conditions of applied simulated lightning current

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Electrical and Electromagnetic shielding properties

The both in-plane and out-of-plane electrical conductivity of CF/PANI composite and CF/Epoxy composite was evaluated using LCR meter (HiTESTER 32522-50, produced by Hioki E.E. Co.) with a four-point probe method. The surface of the specimen was polished with sandpaper to achieve a good electrical contact between wire and composite, followed by an adhesion of copper wires using conductive silver paste to the opposite surface. The measured electrical conductivity is compared in Table 2.

	In-plane conductivity [S/cm]	Out-of-plane conductivity [S/cm]
CF/PANI	148	0.74
CF/Epoxy	25	0.027

Table 2: Electrical properties of CF/PANI and CF/Epoxy

The CF/PANI laminates shows the higher electrical conductivity in both in-plane and out-of-plane than CF/epoxy laminates: 5.92 times higher in in-plane direction and 27.4 times higher in out-of-plane direction. The plane woven fabrics of carbon fiber act as conducting path in CF/Epoxy laminate in in-plane direction, whereas the both carbon fabric and PANI matrix act as a conducting path in CF/PANI laminate, this resulting in higher electrical conductivity. In out-of-plane direction, the physical contacts between carbon fibers in adjacent carbon woven fabric are the contact path in the CF/Epoxy laminate, whereas the electrical conductive PANI-based resin can play a role of conductor of inter-fiber and inter-layers. The high conductivity of PANI-based polymer enables to significantly increase the out-of-plane conductivity from the CF/Epoxy laminate.

As a result of improvement of electrical conductivity, CF/PANI laminate also showed significant improvement in electromagnetic shielding properties. Figure 4 represents a comparison of shielding effectiveness between CF/PANI laminate and CF/Epoxy laminate evaluated in our previous study [24]. The electromagnetic shielding properties were measured in the frequency range from 1MHz to 1GHz with KEC method [27]. The result showed that the CF/PANI laminate shoed the improvements of electromagnetic shielding properties up to 40bB than CF/Epoxy laminate. The detailed description of electromagnetic shielding evaluation can find in our previous paper [24].

Fig. 4: Comparison of electromagnetic shielding effectiveness between CF/PANI and CF/Epoxy [24]

4.2 External and internal damage

A typical lightning damage occurred by applying simulated lightning current of 40kA (Comp. A/5) is shown in Fig. 5; the figure represents observation result from top surface of specimen where simulated lightning current attached. The CF/Epoxy laminate (Fig. 5 (a)) shows large damage consists of fiber breakage, resin evaporation, and deterioration of resin developed from the center of specimen, whereas the CF/PANI laminate shows barely visible resin deterioration just around the center of specimen.

In order to examine internal damage of laminates, ultrasonic testing was conducted for both CF/Epoxy and CF/PANI laminate by using Ultrasonic flaw detector (HIS3 HF produced by Krautkramer GmbH) with 3.5MHz transducer. The obtained C-scan results for CF/Epoxy laminate and CF/PANI laminate are shown in Figure 6 (a) and (b), respectively. CF/Epoxy laminate shows circular fiber damage in diameter of 70 mm in center of specimen. Inside this damaged area, though it is observed that epoxy resin was totally evaporated, the laminate was not penetrated in thickness direction. Surrounding the fiber damage area, damage area that resin was deteriorated because of high temperature associated with impulse current was observed in with of 12 mm. On the other, CF/PANI laminate shows barely visible small resin deteriorated area in center of specimen in 5 to 10mm.

Looking at the internal damage, CF/Epoxy laminate shows larger damage than both the fiber damage and resin deterioration area (See Fig. 6 (a)). The damage forms circular shapes and the size

Figure 5: Damaged specimen after simulated lightning current test (40kA)

Figure 6: Results of ultrasonic scanning after simulated lightning current test (40kA)

was about 125mm in diameter. From the result of B-scope, it can be confirmed that the damage reach to 0.8mm in depth which correspond to 4 plies from the top layer. On the other, CF/PANI laminate shows no defect inside but shows limited surface defect. This defect is corresponds with the barely visible surface resin deterioration previously described.

The major cause of lightning damage of CFRP laminate is intensive heat because of Joule heat effect when impulse high current is flew into carbon fibers followed by explosive evaporation of matrix resin [5]. As previously described, newly proposed CF/PANI laminate achieves higher electrical conductivity in both in-plane and out-of-plane direction than CF/Epoxy laminate (Table 1). In case of CF/Epoxy laminate, only carbon fiber bundles act as conducting path, whereas surrounding epoxy resin act as insulator. Thus, only the physical contacts between adjacent layers of carbon fabric which partially exist lead to expression of electrical conductivity in out-or-plane direction. On the other, both carbon fabric and conductive polymer of CF/PANI laminate can play a role of conducting path, resulting in higher in-plane and out-of-plane conductivity. This high conductivity can prevent the concentration of conducting path and enables moderate temperature rising because of Joule heat effect, resulting in effective suppression of lightning damage on CF/PANI laminate.

4.3 High-speed imaging

Figure 7 compares the result of high-speed imaging of CF/Epoxy laminate (a) to CF/PANI laminate. The first flame represents the initial arc between the tip of discharge electrode and a specimen ($t=0$). The second and fourth flame correspond with the maximum current $t_1=30\mu\text{s}$ and 50% of maximum current $t_2=80\mu\text{s}$, respectively (see Fig. 3 and Table 1). The resulting high-speed imaging shows that quite high intense flush can be observed because of evaporated self-luminous resin gas almost immediately after applying simulated lightning current. In case of CF/Epoxy laminate, the evaporated gas spread out in a radial fashion from the first arc point on specimen surface as time proceeds. This phenomena was keeping developed after $t=100\mu\text{s}$ (5th flame in Fig. 6 (a)) at which finishing discharge process of simulated lightning current. This suggest that trapped epoxy resin gas in inter-lamina was rapidly heated and explosively evaporated could break the neighbor carbon fabric, resulting in the blaze out of resin gas from the damaged surface of the laminate. After the fifth flame, brown off ash dust and debris of damaged carbon fiber with the resin gas can be observed as a black and shadow area inside the self-luminous resin gas cloud.

The result of CF/PANI laminate also shows the intense flush of evaporated self-luminous resin gas almost immediately after applying simulated lightning current. However, emission intensity was much lower than that of CF/Epoxy laminate. Mention that the direct comparison with the result of CF/Epoxy is unacceptable because the setting for high-speed camera sensitivity was adjusted to each test condition.

From the $t=0\mu\text{s}$ in which the first arc was observed to $t=80\mu\text{s}$ (t_2), spreading of self-luminous evaporated resin gas in a radial fashion can be observed. After $t=104\mu\text{s}$, however, obvious development of evaporated resin region and luminous change cannot be observed, whereas the region of evaporated gas of CF/Epoxy laminate showed continuous development after finishing the lightning current applying. At the flame of $t=104\mu\text{s}$, a very last stage of discharging of impulse current, partial bright area around tip of electrode caused by plasma emission can be observed. This suggests that the explosive evaporation of resin because of applied impulse current has been finished before $t=104\mu\text{s}$, spreading of resin gas reason has been also terminated at the stage. This is because the superior electrical conductivity in in-plane and out-of-plane direction of CF/PANI laminates to CF/Epoxy laminate (See Table 1) can rapidly and widely spread the applied impulse current with lower temperature rising because of Joule heating, resulting in suppression of conductive polymer decomposition.

As mentioned above, high-speed imaging shows that emission of evaporated resin gas has drastically reduced before finishing electrical discharge of impulse current. This result indicates that decomposition of resin has been stay in surface of CF/PANI laminate and hardly developed into inter-lamina inside of laminate, as also shown in the result of UT-scanning (Fig. 6 (b)).

a) CF/Epoxy (E-1)

b) CF/PANI (P-1)

Figure 7: High-speed imaging result of simulated lightning test (40kA)

5 CONCLUSIONS

The present study examines the lightning damage resistance of newly developed CFRP with PANI-based conductive thermosetting resin, comprising PANI as conductive polymer, DBSA and PTSA as dopant and DVB as crosslinking polymer. The resulting electrical conductivity of CF/PANI laminate achieve 5.92 times and 27.4 times higher electrical conductivity than conventional CF/Epoxy laminate in in-plane and out-of-plane, respectively. It can be confirmed that the highly enhanced electrical property drastically improves the lightning damage resistance as a result of a simulated lightning current test. The result of high-speed imaging and Ultra-sonic testing indicate that the enhanced electrical conductivity of CF/PANI laminate can rapidly and widely spread the applied impulse current with lower temperature rising, as a result, decomposition of resin has been stay in surface of laminate and development of damage in thickness direction was efficiently suppressed.

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